
HORTICULTURE AS A TEACHING AND LEARNING TOOL AT THE FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHERN BAHIA-UFSB

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RESUME: Sustainability promotes balance between man and nature, encouraging the conscious use of natural resources. On the Jorge Amado-CJA campus of UFSB, students of the Vegetable Production discipline cultivated vegetables under the guidance of an academic monitor and two professors. The objective was to provide practical experience in horticulture, integrating theory and practice in academic training and highlighting the benefits of monitoring in the dissemination of sustainable practices. Teams composed of three students were established, who participated in everything from theoretical classes to the selection of vegetables and construction of flowerbeds. The activity lasted between 90 and 120 days, and included cultural practices, invasive plant management and pest control, allowing students to immerse themselves in the context of vegetable production, in addition to strengthening socio-environmental interactions. The experience developed awakened essential skills, such as leadership, communication and organization, benefiting both students and the monitor.

Keywords: Environmental Education. Plant Production. Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural activities, combined with other human interactions with the environment, have caused serious damage to the planet. One of the main consequences of this disorder is the effects of climate change, which are becoming increasingly evident. Extreme temperatures, heavy rainfall, and the melting of polar ice caps are examples of impacts that threaten the biosphere. In response, an idea of sustainability has emerged, based on a philosophy that seeks balance between man and nature, promoting the conscious use of natural resources (Klug, Marengo, Luedemann, 2016).

Environmental education has emerged as the main tool for the success of sustainability, promoting awareness of the importance of preserving the environment, in addition to enabling society to interact environmentally correctly (Araújo and Silva, 2024). The creation of new educational models that take into account health, the environment, and community development, through multidisciplinary teaching methods, are essential in this process (Chaves, 2020). Practices linked to plant production, specifically horticulture, are some of the ways to spread sustainable thinking, involving agroecological methods; family vegetable cultivation guarantees food sovereignty and greater safety of consumed products.

At the Universidade Federal do Sul da Bahia (UFSB) at the Jorge Amado Campus (CJA), located in the city of Ilhéus-Bahia, a vegetable cultivation was carried out by students of the curricular component Plant Production, under the supervision of an academic monitor and two professors from the Center for Training in Agroforestry Sciences (CFCAF). The objective of this study is to describe the practical learning process in horticulture, highlighting the importance of the integration between theory and practice in the academic training of students, in addition to highlighting the benefits of monitoring.

2. METHODOLOGY

Four teams were formed to carry out this activity, consisting of students from the plant production curriculum offered by CFCAF at UFSB. The students were enrolled in environmental engineering, agricultural engineering, an interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in science, and forestry engineering. The groups were supervised by an academic monitor, each consisting of three students, totaling 12 students involved. After the theoretical classes taught by the professors, the students began selecting the vegetables. For this, the abiotic conditions of the location were considered, and the crops selected were coriander, arugula, kale, parsley, and chives. To facilitate the selection of crops and assist in the management of the chosen vegetables, the monitor provided Embrapa cultivation manuals and support materials found in the literature. With the crops defined, the teachers and the monitor, after a meeting, decided on the location for the beds, which were located near the Jardim das Meliponas meliponary at the UFSB Campus Jorge Amado, located at coordinates 14° 46' S and 39° 14' Ilhéus, Bahia, Brazil. The beds were built jointly, bringing together the four teams and counting on the support of the monitor, and being supervised by the teachers. Specific steps were followed for the construction of the beds, which were cleaning the site, removing weeds, rock fragments and other possible physical obstacles that could interfere with the root development of the crops. After cleaning

the areas, the stage of demarcating the beds began, with the help of a tape measure and string. The dimensions of the beds were 1 m wide by 3 m long. The spacing between the beds was 50 cm. To improve the structure of the beds, the students built walls on the sides with bamboo stakes, raising the level of the bed to a height of 20 cm (Figure 01).

The soil at the site was clayey and compacted, with low quality. The solution was to remove the unsuitable soil and replace it with an appropriate substrate. To do this, 600 g of NPK and 450 g of limestone were used, mixed with portions of soil from a cocoa-cabruca agroforestry system and cattle manure in a ratio of 2:1. Once the beds were ready, the seeds were sown manually. Ten days later, thinning was carried out, adopting appropriate spacing for each crop. To control pests, a repellent solution based on water and garlic was used, applied to the leaves with a sprayer, in addition to manual picking.

Figure 01. Flowerbeds under construction for practical horticulture activities.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The activity lasted between 90 and 120 days. During the process, it was observed that most students had prior knowledge about the planting techniques of the selected species. However, in practice, many faced difficulties in correctly applying these methods. Similarly, Santos *et al.*, (2020), when analyzing the implementation of a school garden as a tool for teaching environmental education, identified similar challenges in the execution of practices related to horticulture, highlighting the relevance of experiential learning and the lack of pedagogical practices focused on environmental education.

To help students with difficulties during cultivation, the academic monitor made 12 hours a week available for assistance, offering support in the practices involved, clarifying

doubts and encouraging the use of sustainable techniques. According to Garcia (2013), academic monitoring is a teaching-learning strategy that meets the demands of university education by involving the undergraduate in the organization, planning, and execution of teaching activities. In this context, this is a pedagogical work in which the teacher guides and counts on the support of the monitor, who, by demonstrating greater mastery in a certain area of knowledge, assists in the teaching-learning process. In addition, this activity benefits the student monitor, by contributing to their intellectual development, improving their communication, organization and planning skills, in addition to deepening their knowledge in the area of activity and increasing their critical and reflective capacity.

The monitoring of the vegetables was carried out together with the monitor, who supervised and guided the management practices applied in the activity. During the monitoring, a low incidence of weeds could be observed, and the few individuals present were removed manually. The students applied the appropriate cultural practices for each crop, including the management, control, and identification of pests. Some insects of the orders Lepidoptera, Coleoptera, and Hemiptera contributed to the learning of the students, who were able to distinguish insect pests from predators and understand their ecological importance.

Insects that were harmful to crops were controlled by spraying a repellent solution made from water and garlic, allowing them to be removed without causing environmental impact and avoiding the use of chemicals. This practice was essential, working as a tool for raising environmental awareness, and by the end of the activity, everyone involved had developed a critical sense about the preservation of beneficial insects.

The harvest was carried out manually and, later, the students presented their experiences, sharing the difficulties faced, the successes achieved, and the lessons learned during the process (Figure 02).

Figure 02. Presentation and harvesting of vegetables by students of the vegetable production component.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Participants gained practical experience in horticulture, deepening their knowledge of cultivation techniques and the importance of sustainable practices, while the activity promoted socio-environmental integration in the academic environment, connecting theoretical knowledge with practical application. The tutoring also brought benefits to the tutor, contributing to their academic and personal growth, improving their leadership, communication and organizational skills, and deepening their technical and pedagogical knowledge. In this way, the tutoring functioned as a tool for reciprocal learning, benefiting both the tutor and the students.

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